

Notes

Synthesis of New Potential Antispasmodics-antihistaminics

NAZAR SINGH, AJIT SINGH and KARTAR SINGH

Department of Chemistry, Punjabi University, Patiala.

Manuscript received 13 February 1972; accepted 4 July 1975.

SURVEY of literature has indicated that no 1,3-substituted secondary aminopropanols of the following general structure has been synthesized upto date.

It is expected that such compounds may prove potential antispasmodics with varying degrees of

antihistaminic activity. With this view in mind, the present study is undertaken. In all, twelve new 1,3-1 substituted amino-propanols are synthesised. These compounds with their characteristics are recorded in the following table.

The synthesis involves the preparation of cyclic tertiary amino-propiofenones by the method of Maxwell¹ followed by amine exchange reaction with aniline and substituted anilines to yield corresponding secondary B-arylamino-propiofenones which on reduction with aluminium isopropoxide or sodium borohydride yielded the desired amino-carbinols. Reduction with sodium borohydride gives excellent yields and the reaction products are easy to work up.

The I.R. and N.M.R. spectra of some of the amino-carbinols are taken and these are consistent with structures of these compounds.

AMINOCARBINOLS

S. No.	Substituents R ₁ & R ₂	m.p. °C	% yield	I.R. Spectrum			N.M.R. Spectrum	
				K Br ν_{Max} cm ⁻¹	-NH	-C-H	CH-OH	δ_{CDCl_3} T.M.S
I	R ₁ = H, R ₂ = H	52-53°	43.5 (a)	—	—	—	—	—
II	R ₁ = H, R ₂ = Cl	71-72°	40.0 (a)	—	3188	2940	3300, 1005	—
III	R ₁ = H, R ₂ = Br	63-65°	79.0 (b)	—	3080	2940	3554, 1013	2.64-3.75, 9-H (aromatic OH protons); 5.28, 1-H
IV	R ₁ = H, R ₂ = CH ₃	86-87°	75.0 (b)	—	3020	2888, 2818	972	(-CH); 6.88, 2-H & 8.05, 2-H (-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -protons). 2.60-3.70, 9-H (aromatic protons); 7.69; 3-H (-C ₆ H ₄ -CH ₃ OH protons); 5.25, 1-H (-CH-) 6.93, 2-H & 8.05, 2-H (-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -protons).
V	R ₁ = CH ₃ , R ₂ = H	89-90°	77.0 (b)	—	—	—	—	—
VI	R ₁ = CH ₃ , R ₂ = Br	50-51°	87.0 (b)	—	—	—	—	—
VII	R ₁ = Cl, R ₂ = H	68-69°	73.0 (b)	—	3160	2936	3298, 1012	—
VIII	R ₁ = Cl, R ₂ = Cl	78-79°	77.0 (b)	—	3298	2936	3392, 1011	2.67-3.72, 8-H (aromatic protons); 5.36, 1-H (-CH), 6.93; 2-H & 8.13, 2-H (-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -protons).
IX	R ₁ = Cl, R ₂ = Br	90-91°	53.0 (a)	—	3322	2938	3520	2.46-3.70, 8-H (aromatic protons); 5.31, 1-H (-CH), 6.88, 2-H & 8.12, 2-H (-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -protons).
X	R ₁ = Br, R ₂ = H	55-56°	78.0 (b)	—	—	—	—	—
XI	R ₁ = Br, R ₂ = Cl	76-77°	47.0 (a)	—	3398	2938	3560, 1008	—
XII	R ₁ = Br, R ₂ = Br	97-98°	88.0 (b)	—	—	—	—	—

Note: All the melting points are uncorrected. All the compounds analysed satisfactorily.

(a) Prepared by reduction with aluminium isopropoxide of corresponding amino-propiofenone.

(b) Prepared by reduction with sodium borohydride of corresponding amino-propiofenone.

Acknowledgements

Our thanks are due to Professor J. N. Chatterjea, University of Patna for recording the Infrared spectra and Dr. H. S. Randhawa I.I.E.T. Kanpur for recording the N.M.R. spectra.

Reference

1. MAXWELL. *Organic Synthesis*, 1943, 23, 30.

Phase Studies in the System $Sb_x Sm_{(1-x)} NbO_4$

A. M. WADFTWAR & K. RAMA RAO

Department of Chemistry, N. H. College, Brahmapuri
and
Institute of Science, Bombay.

Manuscript received 17 July 1972; accepted 4 July 1975

VARIOUS workers¹⁻³ have studied the X-ray diffraction patterns of the stibio-columbite and tried to correlate its structure with the rare-earth columbites. However the present system is not studied by any worker. We studied this system in order to investigate the structural correlation of samario-columbite and stibio-columbite; and to justify the symmetry of samario-columbite.

Spectrochemically pure samples of the component oxides were mixed according to suitable proportions, grinded well and thoroughly mixed by a ball-mill

for two hours using acetone as mixer. The samples were fired in various temperature ranges, at 300° for six hours, 800° for six hours, 1100° for two hours, 1250° for two hours and finally quenched to room temperature in air. The powder was analysed by a standard diffractometer. The diffractometer charts were used to calculate the lattice parameters and to detect the developed phases.

The results are given in the Table 1. It is observed that on introduction of 40% Sm^{3+} ions into the stibio-columbite lattice replacing Sb^{3+} ions in A sites, the samario-columbite phase developed with very faint peaks. On further substitution the intensity of the peaks due to samario-columbite phase increased progressively until the last compound. Various workers⁴⁻⁶ studied the X-ray diffraction patterns of synthetic samario-columbite, but the reported symmetries were inconsistent. We indexed the pattern on the basis of orthorhombic symmetry with the lattice parameters

$$a = 4.45. \quad b = 12.89 \text{ and } c = 5.56 \text{ \AA}$$

The X-ray data of samario-columbite is given in the Table 2.

It is observed that samario-columbite is iso-structural with stibio-columbite, having the structure consisting of samarium atoms surrounded by oxygen octahedra and these octahedra share two edges with one another forming chains parallel to C_0 axis. Each niobium atom is surrounded by a tetrahedron of oxygen atoms belonging to three octahedral units

TABLE 1—The system $Sb_x Sm_{(1-x)} NbO_4$

No.	Composition	Molecular weight	Colour	Phases present
W ₁	$Sb_{0.9} Sm_{0.2} NbO_4$	284.38	Yellow	Stibio-columbite $a = 4.98, b = 12.56, c = 5.52 \text{ \AA}$
W ₂	$Sb_{0.8} Sm_{0.4} NbO_4$	290.10	Pale-yellow	Stibio-columbite + Samario-columbite $a = 5.10, b = 12.89, c = 5.56 \text{ \AA}$
W ₃	$Sb_{0.4} Sm_{0.7} NbO_4$	295.51	Pale-yellow	Stibio-columbite + Samario columbite $a = 5.22, b = 12.89, c = 5.56 \text{ \AA}$
W ₄	$Sb_{0.2} Sm_{0.8} NbO_4$	301.04	Yellow-white	Stibio-columbite + Samario-columbite $a = 5.34, b = 12.89, c = 5.56 \text{ \AA}$
W ₅	$Sm NbO_4$	307.26	Yellowish white	Samario-columbite $a = 4.45, b = 12.89, c = 5.56 \text{ \AA}$